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Assessment of spatial and temporal variations in coastal water quality of Gulf of Kachchh, Gujarat using GIS application

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The monitoring of coastal water quality was done on seasonal basis in pre-monsoon, monsoon and post-monsoon for three years duration (November 2011 to December 2014). Data obtained were applied to Arc-GIS software 10.3 for the preparation of thematic maps to evaluate the spatial and temporal variation in water quality parameters. Cluster analysis showed formation of two clusters which grouped 17 sites in two dominant ecosystems namely mangrove and coral.

[Keywords: Coastal water, GIS mapping, Physico-chemical parameters, Cluster analysis, Gulf of Kachchh]

Introduction

Coastal water has become a major concern because of its values for socioeconomic development and human health¹. The marine environment is a complex system mainly influenced by physical, chemical, and biological processes². Coastal area is such a productive ecosystems and water quality of such environment is considered to be significant with regard to the health of humans and animals³. The functioning of an aquatic ecosystem and its ability to support life forms depends to a great extent on the physicochemical characteristics of its water. Any change in abiotic components reflects in the biotic components of an ecosystem and thus monitoring of the coastal water is necessary. Geographical Information system (GIS) is a computer-based technology for handling geographical data in digital form. It is designed to capture, store, manipulate, analyze, and display diverse sets of spatial or geo-referenced data⁴. This technology provides suitable platform for efficient management of large and complex databases.

A number of researchers have studied the physical and chemical characteristics of some Indian coastal waters^{5,6,7,8 & 9}. However, very few studies on monitoring of surface water have been done in past using GIS application^{4 & 10}. In recent years considerable attention has been given to assess the physicochemical quality of the coastal water throughout India. The present study attempted to carry out monitoring of the coastal water quality of intertidal area of the Gulf of Kachchh (GoK), India.

Materials and Methods

GoK is the largest coastal habitat in the west coast of India in the state of Gujarat (20° 15' to 23° 35' N latitude and 68° 05' to 70°22' E longitude). The GoK, ~125 km long and 75 km wide, lies between the mainland of Kachchh in the north and the Saurashtra/Kathiawar peninsula in the south and is open to the Arabian Sea in the west¹¹. A cluster of nearly 42 islands are present in the southern gulf near Jamnagar and Devbhoomi Dwarka coast¹². Total area of the GoK is around 7350 km². Coast line surrounding the Gulf consists of low-level coastal plains with inundations, deep inlets, a number of offshore islands, and several small, seasonal river mouths.

Water samples from 17 intertidal locations of GoK (Fig. 1) were collected from the surface during pre-monsoon (March–June), Monsoon (July–October), and post-monsoon (November–February) season on monthly basis for three years (November 2011 – December 2014). GPS locations of the sampling sites are given in Table 1.

The water quality parameters such as pH, Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen and turbidity were measured *in-situ*. Temperature was measured by mercury filled glass thermometer, pH with Eutech pH pen 30, Dissolved Oxygen (DO) by Winkler's method, and turbidity by Eutech multiparameter kit. Salinity was measured *ex-situ* by Titration method as per standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater¹³.

The precise locations of sampling points were determined in field using GARMIN 12-Channel GPS

Table 1 — Global Positioning System (GPS) locations of sampling sites in Gulf of Kachchh

No.	Name of location	Site code	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)
1	Dwarka coast	DW	22°14'31.0"	68°57'21.6"
2	Okha coast	OK	22°28'37.5"	69°04'46.8"
3	Poshitra coast	PO	22° 23' 58.6"	69° 12' 31.1"
4	Boria reef	BO	22°24'31.6"	69°13'39.4"
5	Paga reef	PA	22°26'40.1"	69°13'54.2"
6	Kalubhar island	KA	22° 26' 22.7"	69° 38' 48.3"
7	Narara island	NA	22° 29' 07.1"	69° 42' 56.3"
8	Goose reef	GO	22°29'15.5"	69°47'34.0"
9	Sikka coast	SI	22°26'43.4"	69°52'08.5"
10	DedekaMundeka island	DM	22° 32' 39.6"	69° 52' 18.9"
11	Pirotan island	PI	22° 35' 44.03"	69° 57' 22.04"
12	Khijadiya coast	KH	22°31'20.7"	70° 07' 54.1"
13	Jodiya coast	JO	22° 43' 22.1"	70° 16' 46.0"
14	Vavania coast	VA	23° 1' 38.2"	70° 33' 37.6"
15	Surajbari coast	SU	23°13' 07.3"	70° 42' 48.5"
16	Mundra coast	MU	22°48'00.4"	69°34'56.7"
17	Mandvi coast	MA	22° 49' 17.7"	69° 20' 33.8"

Fig. 1 — Map of study area - Gulf of Kachchh

and the exact longitudes and latitudes of sampling points were imported in GIS platform. The results of the physicochemical analysis (three year's seasonal average value for each site) were then used as input data in Arc GIS 10.3 software. The sampling locations were integrated with the water quality data for the generation of spatial distribution maps (thematic maps) to easily identify the variation in concentration by different color gradients.

Coastal water quality parameters were also analyzed statistically using PAST version 2.17c software to assess the seasonal variation. As water

quality parameters were usually skewed, it is more appropriate to use the median as the measure of central tendency¹⁴. It is a powerful statistical tool, which displays the minimum, maximum, median, and shape of the data distribution. The central box represents the values from the lower to upper quartile (25th–75th percentile). The middle line represents the median. A vertical line extends from the minimum to the maximum values.

The term cluster analysis encompasses a number of different methods for grouping objects of similar kind into respective categories. Cluster analysis can be used as an important tool for analyzing water quality data to understand the relationship among sampling locations. The most similar observations are first grouped, and these initial groups are merged according to their similarities. Eventually as the similarity decreases, all subgroups are merged into a single cluster¹⁵. The result of a hierarchical clustering procedure can be displayed graphically using a tree diagram, also known as a dendrogram, which shows all the steps in the hierarchical procedure¹⁶.

Results and Discussion

The average values with standard deviation of year-wise data were calculated for the physicochemical parameters and are depicted in Table 2. Parameters showed wide spatial and temporal variation in coastal water quality. Fig. 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 represents the maps showing seasonal trend in pH, Temperature, Turbidity, Do and Salinity respectively.

Table 2 — Average value ±Standard Deviation (SD) of water parameters (2011–2014)

Year	pH	Temperature(°C)	Turbidity(NTU)	DO(ppm)	Salinity(ppt)
2011-12	8.25±0.67	26.10±3.59	56.62±23.56	7.50±1.02	38.15±5.39
2012-13	7.87±0.22	28.75±4.31	42.49±18.02	8.10±0.54	41.40±5.55
2013-14	7.78±0.24	28.39±4.72	38.02±17.52	7.40±0.46	44.37±5.96

Fig. 2 — Trend in pH of sea water - GoK (2011–2014)

The pH is known as the master variable in water since many properties, processes, and reactions are pH dependent. The principal system that regulates pH in the sea water is carbonate system consisting of CO₂, H₂CO₃, HCO₃⁻, salt content and alkalinity due to borates. Gulf water remained alkaline throughout the study period (Fig.2) which is particularly favorable for fish and other aquatic organisms¹⁷. The data analyses of 2011–2014 shows that pH values range from 7.33 to 8.50 in GoK. The values obtained for pH at all the locations reflected a little influence of season with slightly higher values during the dry season at all the sites i.e. more than 8 whereas during pre-monsoon and monsoon season the value remained in the range

of 7.5 to 8. Maximum values during post-monsoon might be attributed to the influence of seawater inundation and the high density of phytoplankton^{18&19}. According to Balakrishnan²⁰ and Upadhyay²¹ the removal of CO₂ by photosynthesis through bicarbonate degradation, dilution of seawater by freshwater influx, reduction of salinity and temperature, and decomposition of organic matter may result in variation of sea water pH.

Temperature is a primary abiotic factor, showing gradual increase during pre-monsoon and simultaneous decrease in post-monsoon. In present study, the average value of sea surface temperature varied from 22.50 to 32.44°C during post-monsoon

Fig. 3 — Trend in surface temperature (°C) - GoK (2011–2014)

Fig. 4 — Trend in turbidity (NTU) of sea water – GoK (2011–2014)

Fig. 5 — Trend in dissolved oxygen (mg/L) - GoK (2011–2014)

Fig. 6 — Trend in salinity (ppt) of sea water - GoK (2011–2014)

and pre-monsoon seasons respectively. There is a steady increase in temperature from March to June, which peaked during May and low temperature was recorded during post-monsoon (Fig. 3). Lower value of sea surface temperature recorded during monsoon season might be possibly due to strong land-sea breeze and precipitation^{5&22}. Generally, sea surface temperature is influenced by the intensity of solar radiation, evaporation, insolation, freshwater influx, and cooling and mix up with ebb and flow from adjoining neritic waters²⁵.

Turbidity is often used as a general term to describe the lack of transparency or “cloudiness” of water due to the presence of suspended and colloidal materials such as clay, silt, finely divided organic and inorganic matter, and plankton or other microscopic organisms²⁶. Turbidity was found to be the lowest at southern gulf which is dominated by islands and reefs; such as Boria, Paga, Pirotan, Kalubhar, Dedeka Mundeka and the highest turbidity was recorded near creek areas namely Surajbari, Jodia, and Vavniya etc. as it has relatively stagnant water and low tidal currents (Fig.4). Average turbidity in the water samples ranged from 22.50 NTU to 32.44 NTU during the whole study period. It was found to be the lowest at DedekaMundeka (3.08 NTU) during the post-monsoon 2012–2013 and the highest (110.0 NTU) was recorded at Vavaniya during post-monsoon 2011–2012. Higher values were, however, recorded during the monsoon season, which may be due to the fact that coastal waters receive rivers discharge and large volume of storm water.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) is an indicator of ecosystem health and provides conditions conducive for effective metabolism of all aerobic aquatic organisms²⁵. The fate and behavior of DO is of critical importance to marine organisms in determining the severity of adverse impacts²⁶. During study period, it was noticed that DO did not show high significant temporal variation whereas, spatial variation was noticeable (Fig. 5). Study locations were rich in DO and their average values ranged between 7.03 to 8.23 mg/L (66.3% to 77.6% DO saturation). The highest concentration was noticed in monsoon, 2012 (10.2 mg/L; i.e., 96.22%) and the lowest in the pre-monsoon of 2011–2012 (5 mg/L i.e. 47.1%). The Gulf in general is well oxygenated throughout the year due to its large size, high photosynthetic activity, and high tidal effects. According to Desa et al.²⁷ DO concentration levels in the GoK waters are close to saturation varying from 75.4% to 108.6%, which is much higher than the

60% saturation level. This indicates that the Gulf water is healthy.

Salinity is the indicator of freshwater incursion in the near shore coastal water as well as extrusion of tidal water in inland water bodies. Salinity acts as a limiting factor in the distribution of living organisms, and its variation caused by dilution and evaporation is most likely to influence the fauna in the intertidal zone²⁸.

As stated by Kunte²⁹ large variation of air and water temperature and scanty rainfall, makes the GoK a high saline water (50 ppt) body. In the present study, salinity values ranged between 21.12 ppt and 61.86 ppt having higher concentration in the pre-monsoon and lower concentration in post-monsoon season (Fig. 6). During dry seasons, salinity was >40 ppt in inner gulf whereas <35 ppt was in the southern part of GoK. Tidal influence is more pronounced during pre-monsoon with increasing salinity values due to the decrease in freshwater input and increase in rate of evaporation. Salinity fluctuation is considered as a dominant characteristic feature of the coastal waters and the major factor influencing the abundance and distribution of the living organism in marine environment³⁰.

Box and whisker plots were constructed to evaluate temporal variation in gulf water quality. Box plots were generated for pH and DO and for Temperature, Turbidity, and Salinity on seasonal basis as presented in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 respectively. The pH and DO showed

Fig. 7 — Box plot of pH and DO for three seasons (X axis: Parameters; Y axis: Concentration, DO- ppm)

Fig. 8 — Box plot of Temperature, Turbidity, and Salinity for three seasons (X axis: Parameters; Y axis: Concentration, Temperature - °C; Turbidity- NTU; Salinity- ppt)

values well within standards for coastal water, SW-I class (pH= 6.5–8.5; DO= 5.0 mg/l or 60% saturation) which can be used for salt pans, shell fishing, mariculture, and Ecologically Sensitive Zone³¹. Each plot defined minimum and maximum values at the end of the vertical lines and line inside the box indicated median value.

In present study, a dendrogram was prepared among the seventeen sampling sites (Figure 9) and it showed formation of two major clusters. The first cluster is formed by the six sites i.e. Jodiya, Vavaniya, Surajbari, Mundra, Sikka, and Khijadiya which have dominance of mangrove cover. Additionally the three sites Jodiya, Vavaniya, and Surajbari are closely associated with each other is due to their similar nature i.e. they are creek areas having wide mudflat. Second cluster is formed by the remaining eleven sites of GoK having dominance of coral reefs and seaweeds. Moreover, these sites are characterized by rocky substratum and sandy beaches.

Conclusion

The present study summarized the seasonal trend in water quality parameters of GoK and revealed that, the water of GoK is warm, well oxygenated, turbid, and highly saline. Parameters showed noticeable temporal as well as spatial variations in the gulf. Cluster analysis grouped 17 sampling locations into two clusters having mangrove and coral dominant areas. The waters of GoK on an average showed near

Fig. 9 — Dendrogram showing spatial clustering according to water quality in GoK

normal values indicating good environmental condition due to high tidal amplitude and turn over time of water mass. However, rapid industrialization, urbanization and tourism around the coast are of major concerns which otherwise may affect the local food web complexes due to anthropogenic contamination.

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